

A Comparison Between Image Annotation Software for Computer Vision

Oscar Papini

Institute of Information Science and Technologies
National Research Council of Italy
oscar.papini@isti.cnr.it

7th October 2024

This document reports the results of a brief survey regarding various software available for the annotation of images and videos to create datasets that can be used in computer vision tasks, especially for deep learning algorithms.

The principal aspects that I considered were price, licence, ease of installation and use, whether the software exports data in a format compatible with the next steps of our work pipeline, and possible privacy-related issues (e.g. remote data transmission).

The following table summarises the main features of the four programs that I focused on. Then, each program is analysed in a dedicated section, highlighting its advantages (marked with the **PRO** symbol) and pointing out the major drawbacks (marked with **CON**).

Feature	Microsoft VoTT	Roboflow Annotate	Label Studio	CVAT
Type	Electron-based app	Web app	Web app (remote), daemon with browser UI (local)	Web app (remote), daemon with browser UI (local)
OS	Any	Any	Any with Python 3.6+	Any
Free	✓	✓ ⁽¹⁾	✓ ⁽²⁾	✓ ^(1,2)
Open source	✓	✗	✓	✓
Easy to use ⁽³⁾	7	n.a.	6	7
Type of input	Images, video	Images, video	Images, video	Images, video
Export format	Various (including TensorFlow, JSON, CSV)	Various (including Yolo TXT, JSON, CSV)	Various (including Yolo TXT, JSON, CSV)	Various (including Yolo TXT, JSON)

⁽¹⁾ with limited features (see below)

⁽²⁾ paid version with additional features (see below)

⁽³⁾ the author's personal opinion; evaluated on a scale 0–10, where 0 = "not usable" and 10 = "very easy"; n.a. = not available

1 Microsoft VoTT

VoTT (Visual Object Tagging Tool; <https://github.com/microsoft/VoTT>) is a free and open source application developed by Microsoft for the visual annotation of images and videos.

Figure 1: VoTT UI while tagging.

PRO Easy to setup project. Setting up a project is quite easy: the required steps are choosing a name, a description, a source connection¹ that contains the images to be tagged, a target connection that will contain the project files as well as the exported labels information, the tags to be used in the project (which can be changed later) and the rate at which frames are extracted from an input video.

PRO Everything is local. As far as I can tell, the application does not send data to a remote location: if both the source and the target connections are local folders, everything stays in the computer that runs VoTT.

PRO Straightforward tagging. The tagging process is straightforward: the user just draws a rectangle around an object and selects the label with which the box

¹A “connection” is a location that stores data, that can be either a local folder or a location at a remote Microsoft service (Azure and Bing). The same connection can be shared between multiple projects.

will be tagged, then repeats the process for every object in the image and for every images/frames. There is the option to “lock” a label so that a rectangle is tagged with it as soon as it is drawn. In case of a video it is possible to navigate through consecutive frames.

CON **Cumbersome interface.** The main problem is that the interface is somewhat cumbersome: sometimes you try to select a rectangle and it won't work; or you select all rectangles to copy and paste them in the next frame and only one of them gets copied. It is easy to accidentally double label a rectangle (VoTT allows different labels assigned to the same box) and not notice, since the indicator for multiple labels is a small coloured square near the edge of the rectangle. However, I noticed that the more practice I had with the UI, the less mistakes and misclicks I made.

CON **Deprecated.** The software is no longer maintained, with the last version released on 3rd June 2020. It can be downloaded and used nonetheless, but there is no guarantee that it will continue to work in the future.

2 Roboflow Annotate

Roboflow (<https://roboflow.com/>) is an environment for developing computer vision models, covering everything from the dataset annotation to the inference phase after the model training. Roboflow consists of several “apps”, and Annotate is the one used for images annotation. I did *not* set up an account for Roboflow to test it, so all the information here is retrieved from the Roboflow website.

PRO **Large number of tools.** Roboflow Annotate provides a lot of tools to make the annotation task less of a burden for the users, with particular stress on the automatic detection and labelling of objects in the images. However, notice that this AI-assisted tagging may be not suitable for very specific annotation tasks, such as underwater images, and in any case the automatic tagger has to be trained on something, so a first batch of manual annotations is required.

CON **Free version with limited capabilities.** Roboflow has three subscription plans: “Public”, i.e. the free one, “Starter” which costs \$249 per month, and “Enterprise” for which one has to contact their sales department to get a custom pricing. The relevant characteristics are:

- only the paid plans allow for private datasets and projects, the free plan forces them to be open source (which in my opinion is a good practice in the research field);
- both the Public and the Starter plans have a limit of 10 000 source images for a dataset (for the Enterprise plan this number can be customised);

- in case of collaborative projects, both the Public and the Starter plans include 3 users, but only the latter allows other users to be added—for additional \$99 per user per month (and once again, for the Enterprise plan the number of users can be customised).

CON Requires uploading to external server. Even though the paid plan allows datasets to be private, the nature of Roboflow as a web application means that any image or video has to be uploaded to their remote server. Roboflow claims that it “adheres to strict security and privacy standards”, but in any case this is an aspect to be taken into consideration.

3 Label Studio

Label Studio (<https://labelstud.io/>) is a highly customizable open source data labelling platform developed by HumanSignal that runs as a Django backend connected with a Java web frontend.

Figure 2: The Label Studio labelling interface.

PRO Free and open source. The source code for Label Studio is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/HumanSignal/label-studio>). There is a paid

version, called Label Studio Enterprise, that offers some additional features (mainly a better management of an annotation team, the possibility of running the application remotely on their server, and a dedicated phone/e-mail support line).

PRO **May run locally.** The Label Studio application runs on the computer it has been installed on; it probably could run in a (remote) personal server so that multiple researchers can work on the same project at once, using a username/password system for authentication and security reasons. As far as remote data collection is concerned, HumanSignal claims that² “Label Studio collects anonymous usage statistics about the number of page visits and data types [...]. No sensitive information is included in the information we collect.”

PRO **Easy to use interface.** The default labelling interface for images is similar to the one of VoTT, but the order of operations is reversed: in Label Studio the user firstly selects a label and then draws a rectangle around the object. It is possible to choose whether to keep the currently selected label, so that all subsequent boxes are tagged with it; also it is possible to copy and paste rectangles from one asset to another one. Beware that the boxes are *not* saved until the “Submit” button is clicked; in any case boxes and label can be added/deleted/changed at a later time (the “Submit” button turns into “Update”).

CON **No frame-by-frame labelling.** For what I can understand, you cannot mix images and videos as sources in the same project; moreover, video sources do not have a “tag every n frame” option, but can be used for *object tracking*, meaning that it is possible to track the dimension and position of an object that persists in several frames through the use of *keyframes* associated with a bounding box. (However, notice that in this case it is possible to recover frame-wise box information by interpolating between keyframes. Furthermore, it is always possible to extract frames from a video using other tools and import them in Label Studio as images.) The object tracking labelling interface is not as straightforward as the one used for object detection in images; in particular it is difficult to navigate through the video timeline that shows the keyframes for each box.

CON **Difficult to setup project.** Unfortunately, the high versatility of Label Studio comes with the price of an unintuitive process of setting up a new project. In particular, the definition of the labelling interface requires a bit of XML knowledge (though there are predefined templates that can be used).

²<https://labelstud.io/guide/security>

4 CVAT

Computer Vision Annotation Tool (CVAT; <https://www.cvat.ai/>) is an open source images and videos annotation platform initially developed by a group at Intel before becoming independent.

Figure 3: The CVAT interface.

PRO Free and open source. The source code is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat>). Similarly to Label Studio, CVAT offers an online version that runs on a remote server, requiring registration (either with a free or a paid account).

PRO May run locally. As with Label Studio, it is possible to download the software and run it on a personal computer. Moreover, it can be installed on a (remote) personal server so that multiple users can have access to the same project and work concurrently, in the same way as they would with the online version, but without having to rely on an external service.

PRO User-friendly UI. Both in the project setup and in the annotation stages, the user interface is quite intuitive. In order to start a new project, it is sufficient to provide a name and the labels used, then one creates new tasks for the project (which consist of either one or more images, or one video) and starts annotating.

In case of videos, similarly to VoTT, a frame extraction rate can be specified, but differently from VoTT, this is done at task level instead of at project level.

During the annotation phase, rectangles with a chosen label can be drawn by selecting the corresponding button in the UI. It is possible to specify either the two corners of a rectangle, or four extremal points from which the minimum enveloping rectangle is computed. Once drawn, rectangle can be resized, moved, deleted, and their label can be changed.

PRO Can import annotations. Provided that some standard format is used, it is possible to import annotations in the software to review and/or edit them. This is useful, for example, for asynchronous collaborations, where one team exports annotations and sends the produced ZIP file to another team that can import the file as-is and continue working on it.

CON Requires Docker to install locally. The local version of CVAT is available as a Docker image, therefore it requires the Docker Engine virtualization environment to run in a local computer. It is not difficult to install CVAT through it, but it is not as straightforward as a double-click on an executable file.

CON Some limitations of the free versions. Both the free account and the local installation lack features that are available only to paid accounts (\$33 per user per month).³ Most of those features aren't strictly necessary for basic purposes (e.g. some advanced bounding box shape manipulation is only available for paid accounts). One notable exception: there is a limit for the number of projects and tasks that a free account for the online version may have (3 projects and 10 tasks, with max. 5 tasks per project; this limit does not apply for a local installation).

³<https://www.cvat.ai/pricing/cloud>